

Scholarly outputs generated under University-Industry Collaboration in Brazil: a bibliometric analysis for impact evaluation

Gabriel Falcini dos Santos* and Sergio Luiz Monteiro Salles-Filho**

*g138390@dac.unicamp.com

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-9712-8486>

Science and Technology Policy Department, Unicamp, Brazil

** sallesfi@unicamp.br

<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8727-4500>

Science and Technology Policy Department, Unicamp, Brazil

University-Industry Collaboration is increasingly vital for R&D investment and technological innovation. Brazil's limited engagement, according to the 2023 Global Innovation Index, underscores the significance of analysing Embrapii-supported projects. Embrapii, the Brazilian Company of Research and Industrial Innovation, was funded by the federal government and fosters research-industry partnerships. Using Matching, an impact evaluation method, we compare bibliometric indicators of Embrapii-related publications with non-related counterparts. Data sourced from Embrapii and Web of Science reveal that Embrapii enhances scientific collaboration with industry and encourages research tailored to local needs. Additionally, it boosts the academic profiles of participating researchers. Our findings suggest Embrapii's positive influence on Brazilian scientific output and industrial technology, offering a potentially replicable model for other nations, particularly in the Global South.

1. Introduction

The University-Industry Collaboration (UIC) is a type of research partnership that offers significant benefits to stakeholders, stimulates market competitiveness, and strengthens the economy. Promoting this collaboration type is a strategy that has captured the attention of policymakers in the field of Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) worldwide. The motivations for the agents involved in a partnership between Research Organisations (ROs) and companies are diverse. For the industry, incentives may arise through the reduction of research and development (R&D) costs, access to the latest advances in research knowledge, utilisation of cutting-edge laboratory infrastructure, enhancement of internal skills, and increased competitiveness (Hagedoorn, Link, & Vonortas, 2000; Kroll, 2016). On the other hand, for ROs, motivations include access to industrial production infrastructure, opening venues for technology and knowledge transfer, and sharing the risk of projects (Salles-Filho et al., 2021).

Moreover, for the economy and society, UIC can unfold benefits such as increased national public and private investment in R&D, exchange and sharing of scientific and technological knowledge among social agents, and the acceleration of innovative and technological solutions that can enhance the quality of life and international competitiveness (Hagedoorn, Link, & Vonortas, 2000).

In the face of the abovementioned benefits, it is necessary to understand, on the other hand, the barriers that hinder the realisation of University-Industry Collaboration, especially in the Brazilian context. According to the 2023 Global Innovation Index (WIPO, 2023), Brazil ranks 78th out of 132 countries in the global UIC ranking. Moreover, this is not a recent scenario but a historical difficulty that has persisted in stagnation, as asserted by Faria (2021) using

data from the Brazilian Industrial Research of Technological Innovation (PINTEC) until 2017. According to Salles-Filho et al. (2021), the factors obstructing collaboration can be of two natures: asymmetries in strategic orientations and incentives; and transaction barriers regarding intellectual property and structural bureaucracy.

The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2002) outlines a series of public policies that can be established to encourage UIC: financial incentives for collaborative research, cooperative research centres, public seed capital funds, publicly funded intermediaries, among others. In 2013, the Brazilian Ministry of Education and the Ministry of Science, Technology, and Innovation established a policy that created a publicly funded intermediary, which in turn provides financial incentives for collaboration: the Brazilian Company of Research and Industrial Innovation (Embrapii).

Drawing inspiration from the Fraunhofer Society in Germany (Castro et al., 2017), Embrapii selects and accredits Brazilian ROs through public calls. Candidate institutions can be private nonprofit or public entities. If they meet the requirements specified in the calls, selected ROs become Embrapii Units (UEs), gaining access to specific public funding for collaborative research with the industry. The UE prospects projects with companies to develop technologies in pre-competitive phase according to their demands, providing the foundations for future innovations in the market. Each project is financed one-third by each party. In its first ten years of operation, Embrapii supported 2,206 projects conducted by 67 Embrapii Units and 1,500 companies. The combined value of these projects amounts to \$650.000.

This study contributes to understanding the scenario of University-Industry Collaboration in Brazil by analysing the impact of publications derived from Embrapii projects through bibliometric indicators. Our sample consists of 206 publications indexed in the Web of Science (WoS) directly related to Embrapii. Using Matching, we formed two comparison groups very similar to the sample but unrelated to Embrapii, with 611 and 4674 publications, respectively. The groups were compared using bibliometric indicators. Through our results, we demonstrate that Embrapii promotes scientific production oriented towards the national context while enhancing the relevance of researchers in their other publications.

2. Theoretical Framework

In 2006, Kroll published a study entitled “Supporting New Strategic Models of science-industry R&D collaboration: A review of global experiences”. In this paper, the author analyses the coverage by STI studies for these initiatives, placing them in some scenarios according to two variables: short or long term versus pre-competitive research or technology oriented development. In the short term with technology oriented development, we can place projects fostering technology transfer between the actors; in the short to middle-term perspective and aiming the pre-competitive research, there are joint research projects, as for instance was the Seventh Framework Programme (FP7) from the European Union; in the middle to long-term, aiming technology oriented development, we find cooperation in clusters; and in the long-term, with a more institutional strategy and also on technology oriented development, we find institutions like Fraunhofer and similar. The coverage gap is placed by Kroll (2016) in long-term initiatives aiming to foster pre-competitive research. Although it is possible to list initiatives in this area (as NNMI and ERC in the USA, Catapult Centres in the UK, CIC Centres, in Spain, and Leading-Edge Clusters, from Germany), the author argues that there is room for more studies on this type of research collaboration. Our study places Embrapii among those initiatives.

Another relevant issue for this research is understanding and measuring UIC impact. Even if we note a lack of evaluations on policies to stimulate collaboration, the impacts of collaboration itself have already been addressed. In our search, we found several relevant publications, many of which used bibliometrics as a tool. Bordons, Aparicio and Costas (2012) argue that collaboration can increase the impact of research, while analysing the Spanish scientific production in Pharmacology and Pharmacy. Olvera, Berbegal-Mirabent and Merigó (2018) map the UIC academic production, using number of publications, citations, productivity, and the H-index at WoS. Abramo, D'Angelo and Solazzi (2012) propose a bibliometric tool for assisting regional analysis on the compatibility between industrial needs and research laboratories capacity. Co-authorship is a central element for Gielfi, Furtado and Campos (2014) and for Zhou, Tijssen and Leydesdorff (2016): in the first, authors study the Brazilian oil industry through Scopus and USPTO; in the second, UIC in China and the US is analysed at WoS. Finally, D'este et al. (2019) found that scientists that are more inclined towards interdisciplinarity are also more likely to engage in UIC.

Some authors also are interested in classifying and analysing the collaboration per se, in an epistemic effort: Enke et al. (2021) used Scopus and WoS to identify the relevant variables for collaboration in research, as trust, assumption of risks, well-defined objectives, previous experience in collaboration, and communication. Bastos, Sengik and Tello-Gamarra (2021) in turn did a bibliometric search on the production on UIC for the last half century, finding eight research trends in this context. Finally, Brito Cruz (2019) analyses the Brazilian scenario, pointing to a general lack of indicators for measuring the results of university-industry interactions. For that, the author proposes four indicators: business expenditures for university research; papers in university/business co-authorship; patents filed; and start-ups originating from universities.

Considering the studies mentioned above, our research aims to contribute to the gap identified by Kroll (2016) by shedding light on a new Brazilian model to encourage research collaboration. Simultaneously, it aims to address the deficiency pointed out by Brito Cruz (2019) by showcasing a new way to use bibliometric indicators to interpret the impacts of Embrapii.

Embrapii encourages innovation contracts between research institutes and companies, contributing up to a third of the financing of each contract (Salles-Filho et al., 2021). At Embrapii, the process begins when a Research Organisation, which can be a laboratory of a public university or a private non-profit institution, for example, is accredited as an Embrapii Unit (UE) through public calls if they meet the requirements. After accreditation, these UEs start prospecting projects with companies, offering their expertise and laboratory facilities to develop innovation on the company's demand. Upon signing a contract, the project starts to receive financial support from the three parties: UE, company and Embrapii. While the other two parts contribute financially to the project, the UE contributes with infrastructure, materials, human resources and know-how.

Despite having started its activities in 2013, Embrapii is still little studied: we searched the main databases and repositories of papers and reports, and found only twenty-one studies about Embrapii. In general, most of the studies analyse the Embrapii model based on the organisation's public documents, comparing its potential with the Brazilian reality. These studies point to the problems of the national innovation system and argue how Embrapii has the potential to mitigate them. Four studies, on the other hand, collect primary data from

Embrapii Units, evaluating results. However, these studies only look at a few Embrapii Units and Embrapii projects.

This research is positioned to contribute in filling three literature gaps: there are few studies on long-term UIC models for pre-competitive research; there is a need to develop more quantitative and bibliometric indicators on the topic; and there is still no comprehensive study of the impacts of Embrapii on research for innovation in Brazil.

3. Methodology

According to Gertler et al. (2016), evaluations take place periodically to answer questions related to the design, implementation and results of programs already completed or in progress. According to the same author, impact evaluation is a specific type of evaluation that necessarily works with cause and effect. This present study can be understood as a section of an impact evaluation, as it seeks to understand the effects that Embrapii causes on an outcome of interest: the generation and performance of publications.

The impact evaluation methods can be divided in: experimental, which require randomised groups; and quasi-experimental, which work with non-randomly formed groups. For the Embrapii case and data available, Matching is the most suitable quasi-experimental method. Through a large dataset, Matching is used to construct similar comparison groups based on observed characteristics (Gertler et al., 2016; Davidson, 2005). In our case, for each publication derived from an Embrapii funded project, we seek other publications with very similar characteristics but unrelated to Embrapii to compose the comparison groups.

For our discussion, it is important to acknowledge the intrinsic limitations of the method. By definition, Matching can only be performed on observable characteristics, so we assume that there are no other unobservable characteristics affecting the outcomes of the groups, so the intervention is responsible for the differences. This is usually an assumption that can introduce biases into the study (Gertler et al., 2016).

We defined a sample of publications directly related to Embrapii and two very similar groups of publications that have no relation to the Embrapii model for comparison. The differences between the groups can be analysed and discussed as Embrapii impacts. To operationalize the research, we designed the framework as illustrated in Figure 1 below. Our sample of 206 publications was obtained by searching for Embrapii and related terms in the acknowledgements of publications in WoS using structured query language (SQL) in our database.

Figure 1. Research design.

We adopted the strategy of creating two distinct comparison groups, both linked to the sample but with different criteria for each. With this approach, we can always compare the sample twice, adding robustness to our conclusions. Additionally, we can compare the two comparison groups to each other.

For the first comparison group, we selected all authors from the sample, then all publications by them. We filtered to include in the group only publications containing, always linked to the sample publication: same publication period (same year, one year before, or one year after); same research area (meso-level); same document type (article, review, or conference proceedings); at least one Brazilian affiliation. Sample publications were not included in this group, resulting in 611 publications.

The second comparison group does not contain the author linkage to the sample. As a result, the number of publications significantly increased, allowing us to further restrict the criteria for the research area to the micro-level and publication period (only same year publications). With this, from the 206 sample publications, we selected all publications with the linkages: same publication year; same research area (micro-level); same document type; and at least one Brazilian affiliation. Sample publications were not included in this group resulting in 4674 publications.

4. Results and discussion

Having the three groups prepared, we were able to extract the following input and output indicators for each group: document type, publication year, number of authors, number of institutes, number of countries, number of funders, collaboration type, collaboration with industry percentage, open access percentage, number of citations, number of self-citations, Geographical Collaboration Distance, and number of references. For each indicator, we

generated charts evidencing the numbers for all three groups. Below, we present the charts that yielded the most significant insights for our conclusions.

Figure 2. Percentage of publications in collaboration with industry for each group.

Figure 3. Number of author for each group.

Figure 4. Number of institutes for each group.

Figure 5. Number of citations for each group.

5. Conclusion

The findings of our research indicate that Embrapii is fostering collaboration between ROs and Industry in publication. As shown in Figure 2, very similar studies in the same research areas shows a collaboration rate of 5.41% with industry (253 out of 4673 studies in collaboration with industry in the comparison group 2). However, in our sample, this percentage almost doubles, reaching 10.19% (21 out of 206).

These numbers become more relevant when we consider that the Embrapii model does not directly stimulate the academic production, much less whether in collaboration with companies or not. Embrapii's goal is to stimulate partnerships for the development of research projects, and the encouragement of academic production in collaboration can be seen as a beneficial unintended outcome. Since mentioning Embrapii in the acknowledgments of

publications is not required in the contract by Embrapii itself, we believe that this number may be underestimated, with the possibility of there being publications related to projects but not detected by our research.

Furthermore, we can compare the two comparison groups. The difference between them is that comparison group 01 contains the same authors present in the sample, while comparison group 02 does not necessarily. Thus, we can also observe that publications with authors who have previously worked with Embrapii collaborate 2.12% more on publications with industry than group 02, which may indicate an effect of Embrapii on the researchers' network. In this case, we can affirm that Embrapii's objective to create more connections between Brazilian researchers and industry is being achieved.

Second, our findings indicate that publications derived from Embrapii projects reflect a local reality, based on specific and regional demands. The data on the number of authors, number of institutes, and number of citations (Figures 3 to 5) show lower numbers for our sample than for the comparison groups. The lower numbers of authors and institutes indicate that fewer actors were mobilised for the production of the publication. We can expect that publications addressing more global themes indeed require cooperation among multiple authors from different institutes worldwide; conversely, we can expect that publications addressing local issues demand a smaller and focused mobilisation. In this line, it is expected that the publications do not resonate widely, as their relevance may not be international - which explains the lower number of citations.

Finally, our findings point to a higher academic impact of comparison group 1 when compared to group 2. In the same data cited previously (number of authors, number of institutes, and number of citations – Figures 3 to 5), if we compare comparison group 1 to group 2, quantitatively group 1 always performs better. Therefore, we can affirm that authors who have worked with Embrapii present a profile of more cooperation with other authors and institutes, receiving also more citations. We cannot assert that this difference is a direct cause of Embrapii, as it is possible that the order is reversed: because they present a profile of greater scientific impact, Embrapii selects these ROs for funding. Our hypothesis is that both relationships occur concurrently, feeding back into each other.

In summary, we conclude that Embrapii stimulates scientific production in collaboration with industry, and this production is more localised and focused on regional demands and specificities. On the other hand, it selects and leverages the involved researchers in terms of scientific impacts. Therefore, we evaluate that Embrapii is achieving its objective by stimulating collaborative research and promoting benefits for the involved stakeholders.

The Matching methodology carries with it the intrinsic limitation of considering that there are no other elements influencing the observed outcomes. Future studies may complement the analysis presented here by incorporating a qualitative analysis, observing the actors' perception regarding the results and the Embrapii model.

Open science practices

This ongoing research adopts open science practices. The only confidential data are those provided by Embrapii under a confidentiality agreement between the parties, which contain some level of detail about the involved institutions and companies. For privacy reasons, the research only uses aggregated data, without the possibility of identifying their sources.

Data from the Web of Science (Clarivate) were acquired by CWTS (Leiden University) for incorporation into its own database, most of which can be obtained through a simple WoS institutional license. All the data and indicators used are currently being organized and prepared for public availability in a spreadsheet. Sharing will occur upon the publication of this study in a gold open access publication. All queries used for data extraction and treatment in the CWTS database can be accessed [at this link](#).

Acknowledgments

We acknowledge Embrapii for providing the initial data for this study, and CWTS (Leiden University) for the access to the database and indicators. We also extend our appreciation to CWTS researchers Rodrigo Costas, Alfredo Yegros, Jonathan Dudek, and Vincent Traag for their valuable guidance and comments.

Author contributions

The first author was primarily responsible for conducting and recording the research, as well as writing the current paper. Credit taxonomy: Conceptualization; Data curation; Formal Analysis; Funding acquisition; Investigation; Methodology; Project administration; Resources; Software; Visualization; Writing – original draft; Writing – review & editing.

The second author supervised the entire process, from the initial research design to the analysis of its results. Additionally, the second author will be responsible for the final review of the article before its submission to a journal. Credit taxonomy: Conceptualization; Formal Analysis; Funding acquisition; Methodology; Supervision; Validation; Writing – review & editing.

Competing interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest in the present study. There are no personal or financial relationships with individuals or organizations that could have influenced the conduct and results of the research.

Funding information

This research was funded by FAPESP, The São Paulo Research Foundation, through a PhD scholarship (process 2021/11476-2) and an international internship scholarship (process 2023/00077-5), both linked to the InSySPo research group, financed by the same agency (process 2019/04300-5).

References

Abramo, G.; D'angelo, C. A.; Solazzi, M. (2012). A bibliometric tool to assess the regional dimension of university–industry research collaborations. *Scientometrics* (pp. 955–975). v. 91, n. 3.

Bastos, E. C.; Sengik, A. R.; Tello-Gamarra, J. (2021). Fifty years of University-industry collaboration: a global bibliometrics overview. *Science and Public Policy* (pp. 177–199). v. 48, n. 2.

Bordons, M.; Aparicio, J.; Costas, R. (2013). Heterogeneity of collaboration and its relationship with research impact in a biomedical field. *Scientometrics* (pp. 443–466). v. 96, n. 2.

Brito Cruz, C. H. De. (2019). Benchmarking University/ Industry Research Collaboration In Brazil. Em: Reynolds, E. B.; Schneider, B. R.; Zylberberg, E. (Eds.). *Innovation in Brazil: Advancing Development in the 21st Century* (pp. 120–143) 1. ed. [s.l.] Routledge.

Castro, F. P. de, Campos, G. T. de, & Gilaberte, T. P. (2017). A EMBRAPPII como perspectiva à inovação [EMBRAPPII as a perspective on innovation]. *Cadernos de Prospecção [Prospecting Notebooks]*, 10(2), 164–176. <https://doi.org/10.9771/cp.v10i2.17704>

Davidson, E. J. (2005). Dealing with the causation issue. In *Evaluation Methodology Basics: The nuts and bolts of sound evaluation*, Sage Publications (pp. 67–84).

D’Este, P. et al. (2019). The relationship between interdisciplinarity and distinct modes of university-industry interaction. *Research Policy* (p. 103799). v. 48, n. 9.

Enke, E. J. F. L. et al. (2021). Critical success factors in university-industry collaboration: a bibliometric analysis. *Research, Society and Development*, v. 10, n. 13.

Faria, P. (2021). Cooperação Universidade - Indústria No Brasil: suas características e desafios, a partir da PINTEC (2000 - 2017) [University-Industry Cooperation in Brazil: Characteristics and Challenges, Based on PINTEC]. *Revista [Journal] Multiface Online* (pp. 5–36). v. 9, n. 1.

Gertler, P. J., Martinez, S., Premand, P., Rawlings, L. B., & Vermeersch, C. M. J. (2016). *Impact Evaluation in Practice* (2o ed). *Inter-American Development Bank and World Bank*. <http://hdl.handle.net/10986/25030>

Gielfi, G. G.; Furtado, A. T.; Campos, A. L. S. (2014). University-Industry Collaboration In The Brazilian Oil Industry: A Bibliometric Examination. In: *12th Globelics International Conference 2014*.

Hagedoorn, J.; Link, A. N.; Vonortas, N. S. (2000). Research partnerships. *Research Policy* (pp. 567–586). v. 29, n. 4–5.

Kroll, H. (2016). Supporting New Strategic Models of science-industry R&D collaboration: A review of global experiences (p. 44).

OECD. (2002). *Benchmarking Industry-Science Relationships*. OECD. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264175105-en>

Olvera, C.; Berbegal-Mirabent, J.; Merigó, J. M. (2018). A Bibliometric Overview of University-Business Collaboration between 1980 and 2016. *Computación y Sistemas*. v. 22, n. 4.

Salles-Filho, S. et al. (2021). Effectiveness by Design: Overcoming Orientation and Transaction Related Barriers in Research-Industry Linkages. *Revista de Administração Contemporânea [Contemporary Administration Journal]* (p. 22). v. 25, n. 5.

WIPO. (2023). *Global Innovation Index 2023*. Geneva, Switzerland: *World Intellectual Property Organization* (WIPO).

Zhou, P.; Tijssen, R.; Leydesdorff, L. (2016). University-Industry Collaboration in China and the USA: A Bibliometric comparison. *PLOS ONE* (p. e0165277). v. 11, n. 11.